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International technology transfer and its impact on innovation enhancement for firms based in Sri Lanka

Abstract This paper presents research findings from industrial firms based in Sri Lanka who need to acquire new technologies from the external environment in order to compete and upgrade their innovation capabilities. We analyse some of the key challenges faced by the recipients of knowledge in international technology transfer projects from the perspective of technology receiver firms based in a developing country. Through this technology transfer process the receiver firms attempt to utilise knowledge, from the technology senders based in advanced countries, in order to help them upgrade their innovation capabilities. This upgrading process involves overcoming some challenges related to training provision, human resources, language barriers, complexity of transfer process, and recipient's lack of absorptive capacity. We present a number of important managerial implications, especially relevant for technology receivers in developing countries.

Keywords Technology receivers; developing country; transfer challenges; training; language; innovation capabilities.

1. Introduction

It is widely accepted that industrial firms based in developing countries must increasingly acquire technologies and knowledge from external sources in order to build up their own internal innovation capabilities. In many instances this route of external technological knowledge acquisition is via international technology transfer (Medcof, 2007), whereby the firm in the developing country is the recipient of technology from another firm who act as the developer/sender of technology, who is typically based in a developed country. Hence this form of 'inter-firm' international technology transfer should enable the technology receiver to make technological progress and improve innovation capability by effectively absorbing and adapting the technology and knowledge to meet local requirements (Cohen, 2004; Ming and Xing, 1999). However, in our study of technology receiver firms based in Sri Lanka, we find that this type of technology transfer process is often quite knowledge intensive and one of the most challenging activities pursued by developing country firms.

Firms cannot access knowledge from international technology transfer initiatives passively. Importing technology requires enormous effort, especially with more complex technological systems (Malik, 2004). Building a capability with the help of external sources requires a set of skilled activities, including identifying and effectively using those employees who serve as technological gatekeepers and boundary spanners, and combating the not-invented-here syndrome (Leonard, 2011). This means that managers also need to close the gap between the technology as it exists at the source and the form needed to augment internal capabilities, trade off desirability against transferability, and evaluate the technology. This connects to an important issue covered in our study, which is about the receiver fully understanding the knowledge embedded within the technology being transferred, as we found that managers at the receiver firm may not have fully appreciated the complexity of the technology that was

imported. Hence this has consequences for utilising the technology at the receiver unit because it might still be too advanced to fully understand and use.

Much of the international technology transfer literature has investigated areas such as spill-over benefits that resulted during the technology transfer project. However most of these studies have been conducted in the Western world (Daghfous, 2004; Mowery et al., 1996). It has been suggested that one of the greatest impacts of international technology transfer is on project level activities and capabilities of employees to meet the new requirements. Here there is a need to focus on human resource aspects of international technology transfer (Wickramasinghe and Garusinghe, 2010), particularly when this is intrinsically linked to improving innovation capability in firms. In our study, the human resource aspects are linked to *training* and *language* issues, which can often act as barriers to technology transfer, if not adequately addressed.

In order to provide the context for the paper, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by brief discussion on the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings from three case studies of technology receiving firms based in Sri Lanka are presented and discussed. Finally, the paper concludes with some managerial implications of the findings for technology receiver firms in developing countries.

2. Brief literature review

It is generally accepted that there is often technological uncertainty attached to most types of international technology transfer projects, especially when more advanced or complex technology packages are being transferred (Cummings and Teng, 2003; Farr and Fischer, 1992; Lin, 2003). In this context, it is important to appreciate the fact that technology uncertainty can be defined as the difference between the level of knowledge required by the recipient organisation to acquire and implement the technology package, and the actual knowledge stock that the recipient possesses (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004). Technical risks are part of technological uncertainty and these risks are linked to the ability of the acquirer to absorb the technology and use it successfully to produce the final product to required specifications (Bennett et al., 1999). In this paper we occasionally interchange the words 'technology transfer' and 'knowledge transfer' simply because this is the way the phenomenon of transferring technology from one country/ organisation environment to a different country/ organisation has been described in much of the literature. However there is a helpful definition provided by Gopalakrishnan and Santoro (2004), who state that 'knowledge transfer' implies a broader, more inclusive construct that is directed more toward understanding the "whys" for change. In contrast, 'technology transfer' is a narrower and more targeted construct that usually embodies certain tools for changing the environment. Training in use of new technology that has been acquired through a technology transfer project is often seen as one of the main facilitators of this type of knowledge transfer, as this helps to build the technology recipient's capabilities for successful utilisation of the technology (Campbell and Vousden, 2003; Osman-Gani and Jacobs, 2005). This can then ensure that employees involved in the technology transfer project at the recipient site, are able to apply new knowledge and skills learned from technology transfer specific training to the job and the subsequent maintenance of the learning on the job to increase project performance (Aoki, 2008; Kontoghioghes, 2001). This also links to the notion that training associated with technology transfer projects can help to increase innovation capabilities inside the technology receiving firms. As Bigliardi and Dormio (2009) show, in order to innovate a firm must have the right organisational conditions, such as sufficient qualified personnel and sufficient knowledge, where the staff can take advantage of training initiatives.

But the firm must have sufficient financial resources as well as human resources in order to implement such training initiatives, which can sometimes be a serious constraint in developing country industries (Bashir et al., 2010).

Language used within an international technology transfer project could act as a barrier to effective transfer, especially where facilitators from the technology sending organisation are unable to communicate the real meaning behind the words (Else and Fujiwara, 2000; Malik, 2002). Language is part of absorptive capacity, but it is primarily reliant on individual competence (Deeds, 2001). Buckley et al. (2005) found language as a constraint in three Chinese international joint venture projects. Once managers attempted to move knowledge to the shop-floor level, foreign language proficiency was at a very basic level. As a result, all documentation relating to such workers needed to be translated into Chinese, which delayed the process of knowledge transfer and amplified transfer costs. Welch and Welch (2008) propose that regular language audits can help provide a clear picture of how extensive the organisation's language resources are and where they are located. The language barrier can also be addressed whereby the technology receiver organisation has the capability to rapidly translate documentation, such as operational and training manuals, to the local language to help operational staff better understand the information (Malik, 2003). For example, if the receiver organisation is based in Thailand and the technology sending organisation is based in the UK or Italy. Then the receiver must possess the capability to rapidly translate from English to Thai, or Italian to Thai.

Both training and language can be seen as *relational capabilities* that are required to help facilitate effective transfer of technology (Collins and Hitt, 2006; Romijn, 1998). Linked to this is the suitability of the actors involved in the technology transfer project and whether the actors can support both the organisational and technical aspects of the technology transfer process. This is an important observation highlighted by Verbano and Venturini (2012), who add that these actors often require a good level of R&D skills and knowledge, as well as relational abilities. Also a major problem is that proper considerations might not be given to the skills and abilities of the company's workforce, and their likely behaviour towards the acquired technology might not have been properly assessed in advance (Cohen, 2004). Hence this 'human factor' at the working level should not be ignored by senior management.

Though much of the technology transfer literature has been conducted from the home perspective (i.e. technology developers/ sending organisations), scholars have suggested the need of shifting more onus to implementation and utilisation of technology perspectives (i.e. at the technology receiver organisations) (Cohen, 2004; Grant and Gregory, 1997). However, literature on the ways in which firms in less developed countries address project-level human resource and language aspects to deal with new technologies acquired through international technology transfer remains unclear.

3. Methodological approach

It is expected that case study findings reported in this paper will provide a better understanding of project-level human resource aspects of international technology transfer in a less developed South Asian country, Sri Lanka in particular. Based on empirical analysis gathered through conducting three in depth case studies via semi-structured interviews with a number of staff in each of the three case study firms based in Sri Lanka, this paper looks inside the 'black box' of inter-firm international technology transfer to show how this operates at a project level from the perspective of the technology receiver organisation. In particular, we were interested in learning about human resource, training and language

related issues that might have affected the technology transfer process, as well as the transfer process impacts on the recipient firm's innovation capabilities.

The three case study firms were identified from 35 technology transfer projects in Sri Lanka via data collected in a recent questionnaire survey, where some of the questionnaire survey analysis was presented in Wickramasinghe and Garusinghe (2010). In this paper we present qualitative analysis based on insights from three industrial firms. The sample of case study firms identified for our study had to fulfil the following selection criteria: access to information relating to business performance of the firms; access to data such as annual reports and Colombo Stock Market performance to identify some of the best performing manufacturing firms in the country. Also it was necessary for the firm to have been involved in at least two international technology transfer projects, because this enabled us to probe some underlying technology transfer issues relating to experiences of individuals involved in more than one such project whereby they might have acted differently with the current project as a result of an earlier project. The 'technology received' should have been introduced to the manufacturing process plant of the firm or utilised within a new product offering. In addition the technology transferred to the firm must have been in operation for at least two years. In total, ten individuals from the three Sri Lankan firms were interviewed (3 senior managers responsible for devising company business strategy from the three firms; 2 technology managers responsible for R&D/ new product development type activities from two of the firms; 3 manufacturing managers responsible for manufacturing planning and operational management tasks from the three firms; 2 managers with remit for HRM/ training from two firms). The aim was to gain a picture of the experiences of key individuals and to capture the variety of challenges the organisations must face when acting as the technology recipient in an inter-firm technology transfer project. Some of the interviewees were seen on more than one occasion, all at the company sites.

4. Case study findings

As required by the companies interviewed, in order to preserve their anonymity, their names have been replaced with the following: (1) FMCG-SL; (2) Apparel-SL; (3) Textile-SL. All three companies were interviewed through site visits on their premises. In this section we present some key insights obtained from the three cases studied.

4.1 FMCG-SL

FMCG-SL established business activities in Sri Lanka in the 1930s (before the country became independent from British rule in 1948) and it currently employs about 1,200 staff. It produces and sells fast moving consumer goods in areas like healthcare and personal care mainly to the local market in Sri Lanka. In this case we learned about a technology transfer project (TTP) where the technology was sourced from a Western European technology systems provider, with the aim of improving the manufacturing process via the use of a human/ machine interface control system. One of the main challenges faced in this TTP is the fact that the middle to older aged workforce had difficulty in utilising the new technology system on the production line as they lacked computer related skills. For example they had not used any touch screen/ automated systems technology in their working life previously. One of the main challenges faced by the young to middle aged workforce in this TTP was difficulties encountered in understanding some of the teaching/ training terminology of the newly introduced technology, especially in the form of unfamiliar symbols and technical language.

The initial training was delivered by the technology provider and its local agent in Sri Lanka. This training was given to a handful of highly ranked staff in FMCG-SL, which included an Instrumentation Engineer, Installation Engineer and a Maintenance Engineer. These individuals all hold Bachelors Engineering degree qualifications, which are taught in English language in Sri Lanka. Hence there were no problems in the English language communication between the technology provider and the technology receiver company staff. As employee turnover is very low in FMCG-SL, worker motivation to learn about any new technologies introduced in the firm is usually high since the younger workforce has aspirations to develop their career at this company. Hence there is a considerable level of 'buy-in' for new technological systems, even where the manufacturing line Operator worker's educational attainment levels is low as most of this staff hold technical diploma level qualifications and the older workers have long-term working experience. This firm believes that this type of employee trustworthiness helps some of the knowledge about the new technology to be transmitted to the workforce more rapidly, especially for younger workers.

Much of the knowledge transmitted in this TTP is via 'on-the-job' practical training on the manufacturing operation lines. FMCG-SL reported that the company has faced some challenges in relation to some of the training that is given to workers in both a classroom format and during some of the 'on-the-job' training. For the manufacturing line operative staff it often takes time to fully comprehend and learn about the new technology system that had been introduced in the TTP as the workers must go through a lot of trial and error learning, especially during the early use of the new technology. Some of the other local firms have also acquired this technology from the same European supplier. Hence there is unease in FMCG-SL that these other firms might 'headhunt some of their key staff' who have already developed expertise in the use of the systems technology. To help address this challenge, FMCG-SL has recently introduced a policy to fully train at least four members of staff in the use of any newly purchased technologies. Therefore even if one or two staff with this key skill set decides to leave the company there is some support in the form of other fully trained staff to maintain utilising the technology in the future.

Another interesting finding from the FMCG-SL case is that this firm views the TTP as a catalyst for building up the innovation capability of the firm. One strand of this innovation capability relates to long-term interaction with the technology provider beyond the lifespan of the TTP. In this regard FMCG-SL has entered into a contractual agreement with the foreign technology supplier to supply 'critical spare parts' for the next 20 years. Part of the rationale for entering into this agreement is that the cost of spare parts is very high since they cannot be sourced locally and often the foreign technology suppliers will introduce regular system upgrades, which necessitates the purchase of new spare parts. Hence this long-term agreement not only helps FMCG-SL to secure spare parts over the long-term, but perhaps more importantly, builds a relationship with the technology supplier that helps to improve internal innovation capabilities in a number of ways.

4.2 APPAREL-SL

APPAREL-SL is a manufacturing firm that supplies intimate apparel to European and US markets. This firm has 25 years of experience in lingerie manufacturing, making goods for high class niche international markets. APPAREL-SL employs about 800 staff and the vast majority of staff at this Sri Lankan operation are aged 18 to 30 years old. Hence it has a young workforce, but the apparel production industry has the highest labour turnover rate in Sri Lanka, averaging around 20% per year. In this case we learned about a technology

transfer project (TTP) where the technology was in the form of a new industrial machine sourced from a Western European provider, with the aim of improving the quality of products produced on the manufacturing line and it aimed to help reduce costs of the manufacturing operation.

APPAREL-SL highlighted a number of challenges in relation to the integration of the new production machine acquired via the TTP. Initially there was some resistance from the production line operatives to the introduction of this new technology as it meant switching a considerable amount of the manufacturing operation from mainly a manual production line to an automated production line. Part of APPAREL-SL's plan was to reduce the production line workforce in order to remain internationally competitive. Hence some of the production line workers were redeployed in other parts of the business and a few had voluntarily resigned from their jobs. There had been no compulsory redundancies of the workforce.

In this TTP the foreign supplier firm provided all technical documentation with the machinery, including operational and maintenance manuals. The initial training was given for four days by the technology supplier and it partnered with a local training provider based in Sri Lanka to help translate instructional material from English to the native language *Sinhala*. This training was given to a selected group of production line operatives in APPAREL-SL. Here it needs to be noted that the general education levels of the production operative staff is low as only a small minority of workers will possess diploma level qualifications. However APPAREL-SL mentioned that one of the main barriers to this TTP was the local training provider (i.e. local agent), because this agent did not possess sound technological knowledge of the technology being transferred. It mainly focussed its efforts on translation of documentation. The APPAREL-SL staff who had received this initial training were later expected to give training to the rest of the production line workers through a series of one-day workshops in the native language. However, it was mentioned that although this type of training was sufficient, none of the production operatives were fully trained on all operational and maintenance aspects of the whole machine. Therefore some gaps remained in the training provided. Subsequently the technological knowledge required to fully utilise the technology has not been absorbed by the majority of production operation level staff. The skills acquired seemed to be sufficient for regular day-to-day operations of running the new machine. Another challenge that might inhibit the provision of sufficient learning is that APPAREL-SL, like many other firms in this type of industry sector, expects their workforce to achieve required performance targets linked to faster production operations. Hence some supervisory level staff are reluctant to release their production line operatives for further training as this is seen as negatively affecting the goal of achieving the daily production output targets.

After the new machine had been installed as part of the TTP, it was up and running, but not utilised to its optimal production capacity for a number of reasons. One reason was that whenever a fault occurred with this machine, the time taken to fix the problem was quite long because the staff working on the machine had to spend a substantial amount of time in identifying the technical fault. Also because of their limited prior knowledge of using such an advanced technology, it meant the machine had to lay idle for longer periods of time than was originally anticipated. Another related factor is that the APPAREL-SL employees' motivation level to learn about the new technology is low. Part of this problem relates to the fact that the employees do not find much relevance in having to fully learn about the technical characteristics of the new machine introduced with the TTP, as it does not fit well with their career aspirations, since labour turnover is very high in this industry, they can find

alternative jobs without having to invest considerable time in specialising with one type of new technology.

We learned that APPAREL-SL have found the machine purchased in this TTP is now perhaps better suited to bulk production. Since APPAREL-SL mainly cater for the high-end niche markets, the firm finds that it has to regularly change fabric and designs from one export order to another when utilising this machine. Hence APPAREL-SL recognises that their employees need to develop more innovation capabilities that enable them to better assimilate, change and improve/ alter technologies to suit the context of their production environment.

4.3 TEXTILE-SL

TEXTILE-SL is a manufacturing firm whose business activity is to import 'unfinished' textile fabrics and then produce 'finished' fabrics, mainly for export markets. The company employs about 600 people with an average age range of 25-30 years and has been in business for over 20 years. All production is usually made to order to satisfy the needs of the buyers. In the textile industry 'finishing processes' improve the appearance and feel of the fabric. For example, some finishing processes impart a crepe or crinkled effect to the fabric. While other finishing processes include embossing, where raised figures or designs are produced on the surface of the fabric. In this case we learned about a technology transfer project (TTP) where the technology was in the form of a new textile finishing machine sourced from a German company, with the aim of improving the quality of the finishing process on the manufacturing line. The German supplier of this new technology was responsible for the installation and commissioning of the machine at TEXTILE-SL's manufacturing site in Sri Lanka.

TEXTILE-SL highlighted a number of challenges in relation to the incorporation and running of the new textile machine acquired by means of the TTP. The machine supplier provided some early training to a few selected personnel from TEXTILE-SL's manufacturing operation. This training was given in English language and some written material was provided in English. Subsequently the staff at TEXTILE-SL who had received the initial training from the machine supplier began to provide instruction to other production line staff themselves. One minor problem highlighted here is that there may be some difficulties in fully understanding all the knowledge associated with the new technology as English is not the native language of both the supplier firm (based in Germany) and the technology receiving firm (TEXTILE-SL). This particular TTP had not been running smoothly from the time that the new machine was installed on the production line. TEXTILE-SL had experienced technical problems in reaching uniformity in the finished product. We ascertained that this may be due to problems linked with effective absorption of all technological knowledge coupled with the TTP. Also as the new machine had been continuously utilised for production purposes, after a period of time, certain critical spare parts of the machine were worn out, which necessitated non operation of the machine for some periods of time. This was partly due to the fact that TEXTILE-SL had no agreement with the machine supplier to either stock spare parts on site or to have them supplied from Germany quickly. This can be considered an oversight on the part of TEXTILE-SL when negotiating the initial contract, in that there was no consideration for supply of spare parts, perhaps because it was not foreseen that the new machine would be used to full capacity on the production line straight after installation. TEXTILE-SL commented that they were concerned with the high cost of buying spare parts from the original equipment supplier in Germany. Therefore they opted to purchase 'duplicate spare parts' from China. But this led to

a further major problem, which was not foreseen before, in that once the Chinese spare parts were installed into the machine it could not be correctly calibrated. This meant that the machine could not continue to run without replacement spare parts from the original equipment supplier due to technical complexities that were only unearthed by TEXTILE-SL at a later point in time.

5. Lessons and implications for developing country firms

Our study aimed to explore the ways in which manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka address some key project-level issues in acquiring new technologies via international technology transfer projects. The case study findings were analysed at the level of the technology receiver firms, especially in relation to human resource and technical spare parts linked issues and their impacts on innovation capacity building. Although care was taken to select firms with similar organisational structures, industry sector, size and annual turnover, it was not possible to meet the similarity criteria across all three firms. This is partly due to the challenge of accessing firms in Sri Lanka who have little or no previous interaction with management scholars to discuss sensitive internal issues. Even though there are some similarities between two of the firms studied (APPAREL-SL and TEXTILE-SL) in terms of similar industry sectors and size of firms, we appreciate the fact that we could not select three similar case study firms, which is a limitation of our study. The small sample of firms selected can be seen as a limitation, but this enabled us to draw out some important in-depth insights where some of the respondents were interviewed more than once. Future studies in Sri Lanka should be able to build on our findings and hopefully gain access to a larger number of firms to confirm if our findings are more widespread or just limited to a few industry sectors. In terms of findings presented in this section we make the distinction between lessons and implications for developing country firms, by the fact that the lessons are directly arising from the three case studies presented earlier and the implications are not just limited to the cases. The implications also reflect on some important insights gained from the literature reviewed in connection with this study, and may in fact be seen as hypothesis for further testing in future technology transfer studies.

One of the main lessons from the case studies presented here is that although the technology recipient firms make attempts to acquire knowledge, in the form of information and technical support from the technology sending firms, the recipient firms are more likely to experience that the technology sending firm provides technology at a relatively lower cost, but retains a higher margin on critical spare parts. Some previous research provides evidence that the technology sending organisations may wish to protect their stock of valuable technical knowledge and know-how by limiting its diffusion (Cannice et al., 2003). As seen from the TEXTILE-SL case study, the technology receiver firm can struggle to upgrade its innovation efforts because it has procured spare parts from an alternative supplier to the original technology sending company. This results in technical non-compatibility between the original machine and the alternative spare parts. Hence the machine is not utilised to its full capacity and the production line operatives have not gained adequate experience of running the new machine and appreciating its technical parameters to the full, which inhibits their development of innovation capabilities in the future. This also points to another important factor when negotiating the technology transfer agreement. Here it is important that the management of the technology receiving firm have some input from staff with sufficient technical expertise to realize the fact that it would be better to include a supply of spare parts provision in the technology transfer contract, for at least three years after the initial purchase of the machine. Hence, this ensures that the technology recipient does not have to stumble upon some of the problems mentioned in the TEXTILE-SL case. This is seen as a form of

collective learning (Wang and Nicholas, 2005) between the technology sending and receiving organisations.

One of the key human resource issues covered in our case studies relates to training of staff in the receiver firms to fully understand and use the technology that has been transferred to their site. These issues are also highlighted in the previous research in Sri Lanka (Wickramasinghe, 2011; Wickramasinghe and Perera, 2013; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2013). We note a good practice in the FMCG-SL case where this firm has a policy to roll-out training on the newly acquired technology to a number of other staff (typically four other people) in addition to the staff who was trained on it as part of the original installation of the technology on site. This ensures some form of internal knowledge transmission, which not only improves innovation capabilities, but also ensures that if a few key staff with this skill set decides to leave their job and work for another company, there is still sufficient knowledge stock within the firm to cover for this type of staff loss (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2012; Wong and Aspinwall, 2004). Another different dimension of training covered in the cases is the education levels of production line staff. Here it was noted that in order to fully absorb knowledge about the new technology there has to be a basic level of technical preparedness that enables staff at the technology receiver site to fully comprehend the different technical attributes of the new machine in order to operate it and interact with it (McKay, 2008). For example, in the APPAREL-SL case we find that due to the low level educational backgrounds of production line operatives, this firm had to face some difficulties in integrating the new machine technology on the production line as some staff found it difficult to either operate or maintain the new machine as they did not possess the required basic level of education. In terms of country wide implications, this issue shows the need to exposing young people to national vocational training courses which include a higher standard of technical training at some training centres of excellence, which would enable local industry to recruit better qualified talent to their ranks. Sri Lanka should look into other ways of improving training in technical skills by perhaps promoting more government and industry interaction. For example this could be implemented through some form of the *modern apprenticeship schemes* found in the UK and other countries, whereby a company hires a number of apprentices (typically 16 -19 years age group). This helps to ensure that industrial firms can improve the basic educational levels of staff working in craft/ technician level roles on manufacturing lines and ultimately they become better recipients of knowledge that might have been transferred via a TTP. As confirmed by the experience of Scotland these types of apprenticeship programmes are highly regarded by trainees and participating employers (CPC, 2006).

For some lessons arising from the cases studied, we can also make an analogy with the notion of 'open innovation'. In order to adopt external knowledge, which is embedded in technology acquired from an external organisation via a TTP, it would be helpful for the technology receiving firm to consider making a combined evaluation of the technology being acquired. For example, Bigliardi et al (2011) show how business functions like Production, Planning & Control, Marketing, Procurement and others can operate alongside the R&D function in this type of evaluation. Bigliardi et al (2011) add that this enables an increased level of interaction between R&D activities and the firm's other work activities, especially in operational procedures like the implementation of open innovation practices. Hence we could perceive technology transfer as an activity that helps with open innovation implementation. In the case of the Sri Lankan firms studied here, this would enable the firms to better evaluate the technology being acquired if their Manufacturing function could receive some input from other areas of the business like for example, R&D, Engineering, Marketing and Procurement.

Innovation capabilities upgrading may be considered as the principal driver of upgrading the absorptive capacity of technology recipient firms in developing countries. Although this type of upgrading might usually be associated with a move to utilising more sophisticated technologies on the production line, research shows that the building of the organisational and managerial capabilities necessary to leverage those technologies is just as important, according to Medcof (2007). Therefore firms intent on encouraging innovation upgrading, via international technology transfer, need to ensure that their policies support all facets of this type of upgrading. Here it might also be helpful for firms in Sri Lanka if some form of Government policy intervention, via an agency or other organisation, could provide them with advice and support on how to effectively implement technology transfer agreements. This highlights the significance of building networks in a country's technology transfer and licensing community, whereby the Government helps to create a national technology transfer centre or association that can help local firms to not only build international linkages, but then to implement inward transfer of technology successfully.

6. Conclusions

The empirical findings reported in this paper are exploratory and the intention is to generate findings that can be validated and examined in further research with other companies (in Sri Lanka or in other developing countries) using case studies or survey questionnaires.

At present, there is limited research on how firms, particularly in Sri Lanka, can upgrade their innovation capabilities through the mechanism of international technology transfer. Hence there is a pressing need for innovation management research to determine if innovation upgrading is occurring as a result of firms partnering with external technology providers and, if not, why not? Furthermore if in some cases it is occurring, what are the main benefits and costs? Although our empirical findings provide some rich insights into the dynamics of the relationship between the technology receiver and the technology sender within a TTP, we still need to learn more about how firms in developing countries can improve their innovation capabilities to become effective recipients of technologies via TTPs. Governments in developing countries can do more to influence international inter-firm technology transfer efforts in a positive way, with the intention of fostering innovation capacity building in TTPs by addressing training related problems in their country.

We also conclude that senior managers inside the technology receiving firms need to improve language competencies when formulating technology transfer initiatives, particularly with respect to staff hiring; TTP project team composition; and collection and monitoring of training budgets for acquisition of language skills for their staff. Here we need to also consider developments in ICTs, and their application, including feasibility of utilising some translation software to see if this can help overcome any language barriers to technology transfer. It must be stressed that ICTs are an aid that can help in this type of setting, but they do not remove the language barrier in person-to-person verbal interaction, which is also a barrier that was highlighted in our case studies.

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